

Development and application of microbond test for characterizing fiber-matrix adhesion

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SUMMARY

Interfacial adhesion has been studied between glass fiber and polymer matrices, by using a microbond test. In order to reproduce the measurements the method has been developed further. To provide more favourable test conditions the samples have been modified. Suitable equipment has been devised and built to perform the test.

Keywords: polymer composites, surface adhesion, adhesion measurement, microbond test, acoustic emission

INTRODUCTION

The most critical feature of composite products is the good fiber/matrix adhesion. Therefore in the dimensioning of composite structures it is of basic importance to characterize adhesion as accurately as possible. There are several methods to do this, the most frequently used indirect method is the so-called microbond test, where a polymer matrix droplet is applied on a single reinforcing fiber, which is supported by stripping blades of special equipment, finally the fiber is pulled out from the droplet (Figure 1.). Articles devoted to this topic mostly deal with the theoretical or practical investigation of the stress distribution arising in the droplet, using theoretical considerations, finite element modeling or X-ray diffraction, etc. [1-5].

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of microbond test

A real practical advantage of the microbond test is that the embedded fiber length can be easily determined, the stress-concentrating effect of the fiber-end can be avoided and owing to the rotational symmetry of the droplet the uniaxial clamping is also provided [6]. The disadvantage of the method is that the droplet shape strongly influences the

precision of the test [7]. A further problem is that uncertainties in the position of the supporting points relative to each other and to the fiber strongly influence the reproducibility [8]. The stress distribution within the droplet is characterized by maxima around the supporting points and at the entry point of the fiber into the droplet. This can be a multiple of the average value [9]. We ourselves have observed these effects in our tests [10], where the part of the droplet above the support broke down (Figure 2.).

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrographs from the damaged specimen

Therefore the aim of the work presented in this paper is to improve further the microbond test method in order to get more accurate and reliable test method and results, and to ensure the reproducibility.

ADVANCED MICROBOND TEST

By modifying the geometry the disadvantages described above can be substantially reduced if a more uniform geometry and stress state can be achieved and consequently the uncertainties of the test and the sensitivity of the method on the testing person can be reduced. In order to achieve these goals the uncertain geometry of the conventional microbond test has been replaced by a matrix cylinder of well reproducible shape and size, which is produced in a metal plate with a drilled hole (Figure 3.).

Figure 3. The modified test rig

The advantage of the test arrangement is that the stripping blades contact the metal plate, therefore the load is distributed along the cylinder superficies and a uniform shear

stress develops. This way one can avoid the elastic, perhaps plastic deformation of the matrix droplets under the blades, thus the formation of stress concentration spots. The test can be performed similarly to the conventional arrangement.

When manufacturing the test specimen the proper position of the fiber and of the plate is ensured by aluminum „C” frame, which holds the clamps fixing the fiber. The plate is fixed on a fork arm which ensures the parallel and the perpendicular directions in the test specimens. After horizontal positioning, i.e. after controlling uniaxiality the arm can be fixed by screws. When preparing the specimens the drilled plate was fixed onto the arm, then the fiber was pulled through the hole and fixed by clamps. This was followed by centralization and finally the droplet was placed. On one side of the plate (which is the upper side during the test) the matrix – due to surface tension – filled the hole almost up to the surface plane (Figure 4.a). The stripping blades were adjusted to the diameter of the hole and the test was performed similarly to the conventional microbond test. The space left by the removed fiber is shown in Figure 4.b.

Figure 4. SEM micrographs of the test specimen used in the advanced microbond test a) after the removal of the fiber, and b) the place of the removed fiber

By this method we succeeded in obtaining relatively homogeneous geometry, not really depending on the person performing the test, thus ensuring a better reproducibility of the results.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The glass fiber used for our tests was produced by Saint-Gobain, (E-glass, average diameter: $12.84 \pm 1.63 \mu\text{m}$), the matrix was a cyanoacrylate resin (Loctite).

The conventional measurements were carried out with a precision microdroplet tester developed and produced by us, fitted on a universal tensile tester type Zwick Z005, at room temperature, at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. In the advanced test the embedding plates were made of aluminum, their thickness (L) was 200 or 300 μm , the nominal diameter of the holes (D) was 200, 300, 400 or 500 μm , they were fitted into the same equipment and used the identical test conditions. Interfacial shear strength (τ) was calculated from the force measured during the microbond tests based on the theory of interfacial shear strength [11].

$$\tau = \frac{F_{\max}}{\pi \cdot d_f \cdot L} \quad (1)$$

where τ – interfacial shear strength, F_{\max} – maximum tensile force, d_f – diameter of the examined fiber, L – the length of the fiber part embedded in the matrix.

Geometrical parameters were determined by an Olympus BX51 optical test microscope. Electron micrographs were made by a JEOL JSM-6380LA microscope. The test specimens were rendered conductive by gold coating of the tested surfaces.

Simultaneously acoustic emission measurements were carried out with a four-channel device type SENSOPHONE AED-40/12. In order to detect sound waves an ultrasound domain microphone type Micro 30S, operating on the piezoelectric principle was fixed on the blade as the waveguide. The connection between the blade and the microphone was provided with silicon oil. The threshold value was chosen to be 21 dB. Different failure modes were assigned to the signal levels based on the force-displacement curve and the amplitude of the detected sound waves.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

First tests were performed using the conventional microbond test (with droplets, see Table 1.). According to the test results the average interfacial shear strength was 14.28 MPa with a standard deviation of 4.09 MPa.

Table 1. Results of a conventional microbond tests

<i>Conventional microbond test [MPa]</i>											
8.00	10.28	15.17	19.44	9.49	17.04	13.80	16.50	3.76	18.31	17.43	18.32
9.08	11.33	17.81	17.23	12.54	18.04	15.53	17.49	9.60	15.26	15.12	16.11

The results of the measurements of the advanced microbond test are presented in Table 2. Ten parallels were measured at each geometric parameter combination. As shown by the results the average interfacial shear strength was 27.99 MPa at 200 μm plate thickness, and 24.40 MPa at 300 μm plate thickness.

Table 2. Results of advanced microbond test in different plate thickness (L) and hole diameter (D)

<i>D</i> [μm] <i>L</i> [μm]	200	300	400	500
200	29.39±2.37 MPa	31.80±4.87 MPa	28.84±3.82 MPa	21.93±3.18 MPa
300	22.51±5.37 MPa	24.40±2.86 MPa	24.06±2.30 MPa	26.64±5.04 MPa

Plotting the results of the conventional and of the advanced tests in a common figure one can see that the new method resulted in higher strength values and the relative standard deviation became smaller. One can say that the new test method using plate is more reliable and reproducible than the conventional microbond test.

Figure 5. Interfacial shear strength values measured by various methods, as a function of embedded fiber length/outer droplet diameter ratio

The adequateness of the advanced method is proven further by the fact that on the micrographs only the place of the removed fiber can be observed, there is no sign of debonding of the matrix from the metal plate. In order to prove this, acoustic tests were performed to detect the individual fiber fractures and to determine the acoustic parameters of the matrix/aluminum sheet debonding events. The energy of the fiber/matrix debonding was checked by conventional droplet microbond tests, while that of the aluminum/matrix debonding by testing overlapping aluminum sheets bonded by matrix resin. Based on these, the fiber fracture resulted in signals of about 80-90 dB amplitude, while metal/matrix debonding resulted in signal of about 42-55 dB amplitude. During the advanced microbond test there were no signs of either fiber fracture or plate/matrix debonding. Only acoustic events characteristic for fiber/matrix interfacial debonding (also observable in the conventional microbond test) were detected at the maximum force. A common characteristic of these events is that signals of 35-65 dB amplitude are observed during the debonding of the interfaces at certain, well identifiable portions of the force-elongation curve. It can thus be concluded that the AE test results are in agreement with the micrographs, i.e. the failure occurs always at the fiber/matrix interface.

CONCLUSIONS

An advanced droplet application method has been developed, wherein a fiber is positioned in the hole of a metal plate filled with resin and this position is fixed while the crosslinking reaction occurs. When the drop is removed the distance of the blades has been selected so that they support only the metal cylinder around the matrix droplet. In this way the load is transferred along the whole superficies of the cylinder instead of the point-like contact used before, the fluctuating stress field diminishes. The

advantages of the method include higher accuracy, simpler stress field of cylindrical symmetry and elimination of size effect. Several tests were made using the new method on different fiber/matrix pairs and it was concluded that it yields more accurate results of lower standard deviation and the dependence of the test results on the operator is minimized. The results were proved by optical, scanning electron microscopic and acoustic emission techniques.

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